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Investigating the expression level of NF-KB and HIF1A genes among the inhabitants of two different background radiation areas in Ramsar, Iran

Abstract: This study investigated the fluctuation of NF-KB and HIF-1a gene expression between inhabitants of a high-level background radiation area (HBRA) and a normal-level background radiation area (NBRA) of Ramsar, Iran. Sixty participants with the mean age of 48 +/- 15 years were selected and divided into two groups. The group receiving a dose of ≤ 1.5 mGy/year (NBRA) was considered the control group and the target group (HBRA) received a dose of > 1.5 mGy/year. These two groups were from neighbor regions to minimize socioeconomic differences between the participants. Blood samples were collected from each group and NF-KB and HIF-1a expression levels were compared using quantitative real-time PCR (qPCR) based on the stem loop method. The effects of residency duration in the respective areas and gender on the expression of NF-KB and HIF-1a was also examined. The HIF-1a expression level was statistically lower in the HBRA region ($P < 0.0002$), while NF-KB expression was upregulated ($P < 0.0001$). Although the under-expression of HIF-1a in response to dose rate was significant in females ($P < 0.0004$), it was not different in males ($P = 0.74$), indicating a significant difference between sexes ($P = 0.0047$). The upregulation of NF-KB expression related to dose level was also significant for the female group ($P < 0.0001$), whereas it was not for the male group ($P = 0.72$). Notably and as expected, there was a significant relation between longer residency in the HBRA and HIF-1A under-expression ($P < 0.026$), while there was no effect of increasing residency time for NF-KB over-expression level ($P = 0.29$). The dwellers of the HBRA those noted that despite receiving an elevated radiation level were seemingly good in general health, showed some alterations in their molecular mechanisms, specifically HIF-1a and NF-KB expression levels. It is not clear if this is indicative of a beneficial adaptive response and more research is recommended.

Keywords: Low dose radiation, High-level background radiation areas (HBRA), Ramsar, NF-KB, HIF-1A, Radiation adaptation response

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